

Workshop Report

Ramifications of Experimentation into SRM In Light of its Impacts on Existential, Negative-state and Civilisational Endangering Risk

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of its Impacts on Existential, Negative-state and
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by

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Introduction

There has been very little material published explicitly on the interaction of SRM research and experimentation and global catastrophic and existential risk. Whilst it is clear that much research into SRM research and its consequences are relevant to this endeavor, only three papers have been published explicitly on the topic of SRM and GCR [1] [10] [27]. Thus, to widen the conversation and incorporate more expertise, the RESILIENCER (Ramifications of Experimentation into SRM In Light of Its Impacts on Existential, Negative-state and Civilisational Endangering Risk) Workshop was organised.

The RESILIENCER Workshop took place at the Centre for Complex System Studies at Utrecht University on 12th September 2022. It was primarily organised by Gideon Futerman (University of Oxford), with support from Goodwin Gibbins (at the time University of Oxford), Claudia Wieners (Utrecht University) and SJ Beard (University of Cambridge).

The programme involved a number of sessions, mostly collaborative discussions, of which the notes will be published in the rest of the report. The agenda for the day is below:

- 09:30-09:50 : Participant Introductions
- 09:50-10:00 : Introduction to RESILIENCER
- 10:00-11:00 : Discussion 1: What are we even doing and are we sliding down a slope?
- 11:30-12:00 : SJ Beard talk on Introduction to GCR
- 12:00-13:00 : Discussion 2: What would it take to change my mind?
- 14:00-16:00 : Discussion 3: Designing Scenarios
- 16:30-17:30 : Discussion 4: Conclusions and takeaways

It should be noted that the discussions on the day meant that the programme differed from the intended programme. Of particular relevance is the fact that the section on the slippery slope in Discussion 1 was cut out in favour of more time defining what research into SRM means, and the fact that the conclusions and takeaways session ran for between 1.5-2 hours rather than the intended 1 hour.

The workshop took place under Chatham House rules, and thus none of the notes are attributed to any individual. The notes present in this report are non-exhaustive records of the discussions that went on. Most discussions took place within groups of between 4 and 6 participants, often with a note-taker present.

The list of attendees hoped to cover a wide range of academics involved in the SRM discussion in Europe. The attendees were obviously biased by those who accepted the invitations of the organisers, and as the workshop was organised over about 2 months, this meant that the groups attending was not necessarily as representative of the conversation as the organisers would have liked. Nevertheless, the below list of attendees represents academics of various stages of their careers, covering a diverse range of disciplines:

- SJ Beard - University of Cambridge
- Olivier Boucher - Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace

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- Gideon Futerman - University of Oxford
 - Goodwin Gibbins - University of Oxford
 - Ben Hofhauer - TU Delft
 - Martin Janssens - Wageningen University
 - Nikolaj Kornbech - University of Copenhagen
 - Andrew Lockley - UCL
 - Anni Määttänen - Institut Pierre-Simon Laplace
 - Duncan McClaren - UCLA
 - Jeroen Oomen - Utrecht University
 - Daniel Pflueger - Utrecht University
 - Ilaria Quaglia - University of L'Aquila
 - Herman Russchenberg- TU Delft
 - Émile P. Torres - Leibniz Universität Hannover
 - Detlef van Vuren - Utrecht University
 - Iris de Vries - ETH Zurich
 - Claudia Wieners - Utrecht University

The following were note takers at the workshop as well as contributing to discussions

- Juliette Brèche - Utrecht University
- Fiona Román de Miguel - Utrecht University
- Asher Soryl - University of Otago
- Lucia Teruzuolo - Utrecht University
- Jelle Donders

Before the workshop, the participants were asked to carry out a survey, which all the participants and 2 of the note-takers filled out. The data was then used to group participants for the first two discussions, as well as hopefully providing the reader of this report with useful data as to the diversity of the participants attending. When asked their research specialities, the participants answers can be categories into the following categories:

- Small Scale Atmospheric Processes = 3 participants
- Climate Modelling = 4 participants
- Integrated Assessment = 1 participant
- Global Catastrophic and Existential Risk = 4 participants
- Politics of SRM = 3 participants
- Ethics and Justice of SRM = 2 participants
- Engineering = 1 participant
- Wild animal suffering = 1 participant

Note that some participants put specialities in multiple areas, in which case they were considered twice. Moreover, this is merely based on the participants responses to the survey; they may well in fact have written publications beyond what they described as their speciality.

A series of statements related to the participants knowledge and views of GCR and SRM were then put to them. These same statements were presented to the participants just over 2 months after the workshop to see if anything had changed. However, this secondary survey did not get enough responses (8) for a meaningful comparison, so only the results of the initial survey will be shown. This initial survey is shown in Appendix 1.

2

The Workshop Discussions

2.1. Discussion 1: What are we even doing?

The first discussion saw the participants discussing what actually constituted SRM research. They were allocated into 4 groups, and given a set of descriptions of experiments and scenarios to discuss for the first half of the session. The groups were then switched and they discussed definitions of SRM research.

The prompts they were given are in Appendix 2

2.1.1. Summary of the discussion

Many participants rejected the utility of having a definition of SRM research, and suggested that a number of the risks of research come from its conceptualisation and communication rather than in the methodologies and specific objects of study of the research; thus a definition in isolation of each given case may not be possible. Those risks which didn't originate from the imagining of SRM could be dealt with without a definition of SRM research, as these are risks whether the research is "SRM research" or not, once again reducing the utility of a definition.

It was suggested a definition was not really possible, as all research relates to other disciplines, so a clear disciplinary delineation doesn't really exist. This was supported by the common agreement in the group that SRM research can often physically look identical to other forms of research, such as volcanology, climate science and ecosystem science. Thus, a worry was raised that defining SRM research as "research that could be relevant to SRM" would lead to blocking of, or cumbersome governance of, a lot of important climate and earth science research, such as volcanology or atmospheric physics.

Others suggested that a definition was indeed needed, as a definition may be an important prerequisite for governance, but that this definition should and could be much more closely related to the researchers' conceptions of the research they are doing. This was supported both by those who suggests all research is inherently coloured by the researchers' own normative positions and assumptions, and those who were concerned about a definition based on physical characteristics of SRM research constraining basic science research. Thus, there was discussion as to where we ought to imagine the "lines" lie. One suggested SRM research had to be defined "in the context of climate change", whilst a few other discussed the potential importance of the intentions of researchers, one arguing that if SRM research wasn't defined in relation to researchers intentions, studying sulfuric acid clouds on Venus would constitute SRM research. It was further discussed that researchers intentions may be what is morally significant rather than the impact of a given experiment, and that a definition expressing this may be useful.

The discussion of the importance of the intention of researched branched out into considerations of slippery slope, responsibility and governance. One participant questioned who's responsibility it is to think about policy impacts when researchers may be plausibly naive towards the policy implications of their research, such as in Description 1. Similarly, the role of ethics boards, universities and funders as dictators of what was and wasn't SRM research (or unacceptably risky research) was suggested as

being of relevance, both in terms of how the slippery slope manifests and in utilising research definitions as a governance mechanism.

In this context, it was suggested that the definition of SRM research is itself governance. It was suggested that what type of governance (and thus by extension, what sort of definition) was necessary for SRM research was a function of how it influenced negotiations, and so some suggested that modelling was more impactful on this axis (and thus plausibly more dangerous) than outdoor experimentation. The type of model used and the communication of this modelling to political leaders, including the communication of epistemic uncertainties, was seen both as key communication challenges and potential risks of modelling research. There was, however, little discussion of how to practically govern modelling despite a recognition it was plausibly more dangerous than experimentation. Moreover, the necessity of modelling to communicate risk was also discussed as a way to prevent a slippery slope, meaning modelling could be seen as dual-use with reference to making deployment more likely or not.

The responsibility of researchers self-governance to consider steps taken downstream of carrying out the research was also considered, such as where you publish, as potentially important considerations for the impact of research. Moreover, the responsibility of researchers to engage with critical viewpoints was discussed as more important in SRM than most other areas of science. Some questioned whether researchers have a responsibility if they can reasonably suspect their research could be used for something they don't agree with, or whether they have a duty to be impartial conveyers of information. Some questioned whether such impartiality can ever exist, and if it can't, argued being explicit about the subjectivity and normativity of all research was important.

There was some discussion of how to deal with the relevance of actors outside the control of the SRM research community and how much responsibility the community had over this. Much modelling, and thus the validity of many narratives around SRM, is contingent on CDR, which it was noted has less conservative communication norms than SRM, which may influence the ability for the field's self-governance to have the desired effect of reducing mitigation deterrence.

Participants both put forward and questioned the utility of considerations of moral hazard and mitigation deterrence around research; some questioned whether such mitigation deterrence was even possible as they believed fossil fuel phase out was a matter of economic inevitability, whilst others questioned whether a reverse moral hazard was not equally as likely.

2.1.2. Tripartite Framework

Introduction of Framework

Gideon Futerman introduced the Tripartite Framework using the diagram in Appendix 3. A description of the framework from an unpublished draft is also seen in Appendix 3.

Discussion of Tripartite Framework

A key criticism of the framework brought up by a number of participants was that the separation of the categories implied that these aspects of research were separate from one another. This was despite the intention of Gideon Futerman (the framework's origin) that the framework saw each aspect of the research ecosystem as inherently interlinked. Many, however, felt that the very act of linguistically separating them constructed that difference as possible, and would encourage observers to silo these aspects out. Moreover, it was raised that what these categories are doing is actually fundamentally different for each of the categories, so treating them as three equal and parallel aspects of the research ecosystem is questionable. As a result, integrating them, rather than viewing them as distinct but interconnected, may be a more effective visualisation and conceptualisation. For example, it was raised that communication permeates everything, and research is always situated in a community; thus, it may be better conceptualised through communication linking different actors in the ecosystem together, where some of those actors carry out research. To do this, however, may require greater specificity of whom the actors are, what their power relations are to one another and what discourses are involved shaping the social world.

Others criticised the lack of an "outside world" in the framework, saying the lack of dynamic relationship between research and the outside world was the "biggest problem with this framework". Particularly sharp criticism was reserved for the lack of real definition of where funders fit in, as it was felt that lumping them in either part of the Communities, or the outside world was insufficient to defining their power over the overall ecosystem. Moreover, in placing publics who are outside the Communities as mere receivers of research and communication, rather than active participants in

the research process, whether knowingly or not, was seen as descriptively and normatively suspect. The lack of the presence of NGOs, companies, funders and politicians with interest in SRM in the framework was also considered as a weakness; whilst it is arguable these were intended to be part of the Communities, it was felt that their presence should be more explicit, and their role is sufficiently different to other actors in the Communities that they should be unique. One suggestion was to do away with the concept of Communities, and rather have a map of different plausibly relevant actors, some which are defined by the Communities concept, others not. However, to do this, it was generally suggested that greater specificity to what the landscape of these actors look like in reality, and their power relations and discourses involved, something which the more general tripartite framework failed to do.

Others simply felt the framework did not address the most important questions. Despite the framework attempting to be a tool for different normative ends, it was felt that one cannot usefully define the SRM ecosystem merely structurally, without reference to the imaginings, discourses and power relations those within it hold, as the Tripartite Framework attempts to do. Rather, it was argued, one has to address what actors in the ecosystem were actually attempting to do, and which actual discourses were involved in this. Engagement with imaginings of SRM, which is missing from the framework, were seen as essential, meaning relevant questions that this framework relegates to fitting into structural categories includes: what research is for, who we are trying to generate it for, what sorts of questions are being asked and why. Questions of power were also not present in the framework, which many participants saw as essential aspect of the research landscape. Similarly, some suggested that intention of the communities, individuals and research projects matters a lot, although it is unclear if this point was due to its impacts on the overall end result or an ethical consideration of intentions, something which the framework deliberately deemphasised. Finally, there was some discussion also about the failure of the framework to account for deliberate misinformation or lack of responsibility around framings of SRM, again suggesting that the purely structural model of the research ecosystem ignoring these important aspects of ethical responsibility was an inherent weakness of the framework.

2.2. Presentation on GCR

The Presentation SJ Beard gave on GCR is in Appendix 4.

2.3. What would convince me that I'm wrong

In this session, participants were broadly grouped based on their responses to the survey. They were asked to discuss their present views, and what may convince them that they are wrong. Then, the groups were mixed up, with participants asked to share these thoughts, and specifically talk about SRM and Global Catastrophic and Existential Risk, as well as identify cruxes of disagreement.

2.3.1. Views of participants on SRM research

Whilst the survey gave a quantitative analysis of participants views on SRM research and deployment, in this section, a more qualitative description of some of the arguments present in the discussion are made.

A large number of participants had positive attitudes towards SRM research. Many saw a qualitative difference between how we should treat SRM research and its deployment, with a number of participants stating support for SRM research but not deployment. Some suggest that because some SRM research is very far from deployment, and other aspects of research very close, and thus regulation of research is needed

There were a number of arguments presented in favour of research. A number of participants suggested that research was needed to "find out what works and doesn't work", that research discovers interesting and useful information that may inform policy, or that it is necessary to reduce uncertainties and unknowns of SRM. Some suggested that deployment would not be possible without research, and if we want to keep the option of deployment open (some suggested this was necessary as "insurance"), then research is necessary. Contrary to this, it was argued that policy decisions, such as those in the pandemic, are often made without research, so carrying out research may act to make policy more science-informed without actually changing the probability of deployment, which makes research a more important prospect. There were general themes of freedom of research from many participants, and that SRM research governed effectively was at least a palatable or moderately attractive prospect.

There were a variety of views on the inevitability of SRM research and its relation to deployment and policy. One participant suggested that SRM research was inevitable and that there weren't powers who control it, so they worried about researchers and their interests and how to control this. Another suggested it was hard to limit research, although this was opposed by the suggestion that policy to regulate SRM research was possible. One participant who was in favour of SRM research but wanted to keep it away from mainstream climate discussions proposed keeping SRM research "in the drawer", although it was questioned whether this is possible, or whether it is inevitable that once SRM is researched it enters policy discussions. This question is rather similar to the concept of the slippery slope, which was raised by a few participants, although others suggested that research might discover negatives to SRM that may make deployment less likely rather than more likely, so a unidirectional slippery slope was far from inevitable. It was also suggested that SRM research may be useful to inform policy in an ideal world, but in our irrational geopolitical order, may complicate negotiations.

There were also discussion with regards to whether deployment was desirable and what this could look like. One participant suggested deployment would look like insurance rather than a pillar of climate policy. Many participants were against deployment, particularly before a considerable amount of research had been done, and presented worries that the current climate emergency framing may justify premature deployment. Others focused on the power dynamics, and it was suggested that SRM may cause grossly inequitable or unstable power structures, and that there was a significant risk of SRM causing major geopolitical instability no matter how it is deployed. Moreover, there was questioning whether governance of deployment can ever be global, multilateral and democratic, given the undemocratic nature of the international order.

2.3.2. Cruxes

One set of cruxes can be seen as regarding the probable state of the climate. Many suggested that whether we had a high probability of staying below certain temperature targets (1.5 or 2C) may be a key point which would make them considerably more sceptical of the utility of SRM research. Others focused on climate impacts, particularly tipping points, at potentially low levels of warming, as things that would make them more favourable of research. Questions of climate politics were important for another, who felt that if systemic changes to address climate change were taken, they would after that support SRM research.

Others focused on arguments more related to the governance of SRM deployment. Some suggested that if they were convinced that a governance scheme to govern overshoot including SRM could be set up that wouldn't suffer from the same problems of coordination that mitigation suffers, then they may be more favourable towards SRM research. Another suggested that if they felt there were robust measures in place that would give them assurances rogue actors couldn't unilaterally deploy they would be less positive towards SRM research. Another suggested that the problem of many simultaneous independent regional deployments was an important consideration as to why they considered deployment very likely, and so if this was seen as implausible, this would reduce how important they saw research. The question of whether regional deployment could slide into global deployment was also raised as a crux as to why another participant was wary of large scale experimentation, as they saw it as potentially an irreversible slippery slope, with not a binary on/off switch between research and deployment, but rather the separation being a much fuzzier spectrum. A number of participants raised the idea that if it could be shown that there was a feasibly democratic mechanism to govern decisions around deployment, they may be more convinced of the acceptability of SRM, or whether there were democratic decision-making procedures over what constituted an "emergency" whereby SRM were to be deployed under those conditions.

A large number of arguments focused on research and its governance. A number of participants (particularly those who took a more positivist worldview) suggested that if it could be proven the moral hazard and slippery slope was a significant issue, this would at least somewhat reduce their support for SRM research. Another, who viewed SRM research as broadly inevitable, suggested that if they were more convinced a research moratorium could work, their attitudes towards research governance would change. It was also suggested that if researchers in the field were more explicit about their normative positions and willing to cede more power to those outside the field, then this might prove the current processes could responsibly address many of the problems of research, so might convince that participant that research was plausibly a good idea.

Others focused on whether SRM research could do anything to meaningfully address any of the key

risks of SRM. Unknown unknowns were suggested as a key risk of SRM, something which research may be unable to ameliorate, or that risks may only become salient due to later events, and thus may be underprioritised in research. Moreover, inherent uncertainty with regards to lack of control of the impacts of SRM, and thus whether we can ever be certain enough to deploy, was raised, although another participant suggested that as SRM pushed conditions closer to pre-industrial, uncertainties should be lower than unabated climate change.

2.3.3. SRM relation to GCR

Participants were then asked to discuss their views on the relation of SRM to Global Catastrophic Risk (GCR) and the impact that this consideration might have on their overall views; this was following a presentation by SJ Beard between Discussion 1 and Discussion 2.

Some views of the interaction of SRM and GCR focused on SRM's interaction with vulnerabilities. One participant suggested that SRM could have two different impacts on geopolitical power which may effect the vulnerabilities of the world to specific hazards. SRM may centralise power in a single or a small number of powerful countries or institutions, increase the vulnerability of the world to a hazard that significantly effected that node in the global system. Or SRM could lead to a more multipolar world, making the world system more anarchic, which may make global coordination and governance harder, and so increase global vulnerability that way. Another suggested that SRM more strongly couples the global socio-economic-geopolitical system with the ecological-climatic system, thus allowing for greater vulnerability of the global spread of a catastrophe, once again increasing our vulnerability.

The potential for counter-geoengineering to be used, thus snowballing into conflict or catastrophic climate disruption was suggested, although one participant rejected that counter geoengineering could be used to deliberately cause targeted harm, so was unlikely to actually be deployed (as its not a realistic deterrent) and thus wasn't as major a contributor to risk as thought. Others, however, did discuss the possibility for SRM to cause conflict, although most of the discussion of conflict was reserved for discussion 3.

Whether SRM could contribute to GCR through its physical or climatic effects was also discussed. "Wrong" deployment of SRM, such as injecting in one hemisphere thus causing a global catastrophe due to crop failure or change in atmospheric circulation leading to water shortages, was generally rejected as implausible, although the possibility of unforeseen or unforeseeable effects of "safe" deployment schemes was considered plausible. It was also discussed that whilst in median cases the physical effect of SRM may be beneficial at reducing climate damages, at the extremes, where termination shock occurs, the rapid warming may be enough to trigger events to cause a global catastrophe. There was, however, little discussion of the exact pathway to catastrophe from termination, although the catastrophic potential of a large termination shock was generally agreed upon. However, one participant did suggest they felt the risk of and risks from termination shock were generally overhyped.

Many questioned the concept of GCR and how it should be prioritised in relation to SRM. Some participants had fundamental axiological differences with the typical GCR framing, suggesting that given the harm humanity caused to wild animals, a global catastrophe may in fact be desirable, rather than (as the concept of GCR implies) disastrous. Moreover, the assumption made by many who discuss GCR is that industrial civilisation is desirable, and this normative position was also questioned by a few participants. One participant suggested that GCR assumes a particular view of normality that is white, western and patriarchal, and that it can lead to conclusions that are very "white man's burden", such as that SRM must be used to "save the world". Interestingly, the assumption here was that in discussions of SRM and GCR, the focus would be on whether SRM would be used to save the world from a global catastrophe, whereas many participants focused on the potential for SRM to contribute to GCR.

It was also questioned under what conditions where reduction of GCR by SRM may be ethically considered to override democracy; this discussion was often done either under the assumption SRM was inherently undemocratic, or discussing cases where rapid deployment of SRM may be warranted. One participant suggested that global extinction would have to be near certain for other ethical considerations to not also have to be taken into account alongside GCR. A lesser condition, that SRM could be known to avoid a tipping point was raised as more appropriate. However, under both of these, the question of whether these worries, which are mediated through experts, could justifiably override democratic decision making was raised. This was countered by other participants who saw the continued use of fossil fuels as status quo bias, and so suggested that given neither state (SRM or the status quo) exists with democratic approval, then perhaps SRM to avoid catastrophe could be justified. A further point

was raised, similar to perspectives that suggest SRM may exist to reduce our vulnerability to climate change, as to whether it may be justifiable to deploy SRM to increase stability, even if it is deployed undemocratically, as this stability acts to reduce GCR.

Interestingly, those groups which questioned the ethical validity of the GCR concept in relation to SRM tended to focus on the potential of SRM to avoid global catastrophe, whereas other groups tended to focus on the potential of SRM to increase GCR. Those participants that focused on SRM's potential to increase GCR who also criticised the focus on GCR, tended to do so from the perspective that it reduced focus on the more likely impacts of climate change; these participants tended to be more favourable to the concept of SRM as well. Interestingly, therefore, those who were more favourable to the concept of SRM tended to focus on the contribution of SRM to increasing GCR in this discussion, and those who were more against SRM tended to focus on the GCR concept being used to justify the usage of SRM.

2.4. Discussion 3: Scenario Design

2.4.1. Quick ideas of scenarios

First, participants were asked to come up with a list of scenario ideas that they were interested in that might feasibly impact on SRM's relation to GCR. They were told to come up with short statements and ideas without specifying the scenarios too much. A selection of these are below:

- A flicking of some tipping point in the earth system whilst SRM is not deployed but could have been
- A major country pulls out of SRM governance scheme whilst SRM is being deployed
- A governance scheme is stress tested by an exogenous event, such as a volcano or a space weather event
- Neoliberal revival and a market world where SRM is a tradable commodity
- Scenarios exploring SRM's impact on other sentient creatures (ie animals)
- Three countries demanding near-term SRM intervention to provide climatic relief; China, India, Pakistan may be countries of interest
- A world where climate action has been increasingly securitized, and SRM is seen as a matter of defence/national security
- A world where climate sensitivity is high
- A scenario where SRM works, but is regionally varied, so there are communication issues getting broad global support for the scheme
- SRM in a world with stalling economic growth in middle income countries
- Scenarios exploring how politicians react to scientific information, and how this may feedback into the scientific process
- Scenarios exploring scientific communication to the public and politicians
- A private actor with financial means thinks SRM is a good idea
- A world where SRM is being carried out but NETs fail to materialise at scale
- A disruption akin to the war in Ukraine occurs during SRM deployment
- Unforeseen events (perhaps even unforeseeable) occur during SRM deployment
- Unexpected pattern changes in the dynamics of climate change that were not forecasted or reasonable from model
- Carrying out SRM on another planet

2.4.2. More detailed scenario design

Group 1- Existing Governance Structure has to deal with climatic events

One group discussed possible scenarios where an already existent governance scheme is dealt an exogenous climatic shock, so is stress tested.

There was a strong desire for variation in the types of governance system explored, including:

- Unilateral Deployment
- Minilateral Deployment

- Multilateral Deployment
- Technocratic 'Central Bank of SRM' style governance
- Democratic governance

Moreover, there was interest in a range of natures of governance mechanisms, ranging the whole spectrum from banning SRM research and deployment to centralized deployment or decentralised market based deployment. Moreover, questions of which mechanism and institution and how binding governance mechanisms would be was discussed as a key factor in the scenarios. It was proposed that backcasting could be used to explore how these governance mechanisms could emerge, and what conditions allow for which governance mechanisms to emerge. The reasons why agreements emerge could be parsed out by backcasting, including why different countries agreed, such as agreement because it was believed governance would be beneficial, agreement due to international pressure or agreement on the belief SRM would not be used. The idea here is the history of an agreement may be important in how or whether it sustains or breaks down.

There was interest in exploring different features of how these governance systems what respond to climatic or non-climatic shocks. There was interest whether there was a trade off between democracy and responsiveness, how neoliberal or authoritarian governance might effect responses, which sorts of governance systems were best at responding to which sorts of shocks, and whether any system would be resilient to some of the worse shocks. The shocks discussed included:

- Sustained breakdown in global communications
- Volcanic Eruption during SRM deployment
- Space Weather Events
- Climate Sensitivity is higher than expected
- Tipping Points are hit
- Breakdown of Global Cooperation (ie war)

A game-like scenario was proposed to explore technocratic decision making, where backcasting would be used to describe the exact governance mechanism, bindingness of the mechanism and purview of the governance body created. Then, three groups (technocrats, scientists and military/geopolitical figures) would interact in a three way coupled game. The technocrats would make deployment decisions, informed by the advice of scientists and informed, pressured and reacting to military and geopolitical advisors from their own countries. This governance scheme would then have to try and react to various of the shocks described above, to stress test the scheme. The reasoning was that this is sufficiently similar to many proposed governance mechanisms to act as a useful idealised model, and the hope would be to use genuine (former) UN officials (technocrats), SRM scientists and hopefully military/geopolitical advisors, so the people playing the roles are good models of the people who are likely to fill said roles in the real world.

Group 2- Speculative SRM in the Far(-ish) Future

Another group discussed end-of century scenarios for SRM. This group, in their discussions, raised the problem of making scenarios realistic given how far away they are from now. The issue of major technology development, such as nuclear fusion, was raised, as was the idea that if SRM was still on the agenda in 2100, it was hard to see that it wouldn't have been deployed. There was also a suggestion that decarbonisation would likely be well underway towards the end of the century, so the scenarios would be exploring SRM in a very different capacity to present day imaginings.

This group also discussed how the relevant differences in governance between decarbonisation and SRM may be an interesting factor to explore. In particular, they suggested decarbonisation is about how much effort to put into transitioning away from a carbon economy (input), whilst SRM is about the consequences of an intervention (output), and thus the governance issues here will be interesting to explore. Moreover, they explored how the precautionary principle, particularly around Earth System tipping points, might push early SRM deployment, once again meaning the status quo around SRM in 2100 is likely to be radically different to today.

Group 3- How do Politicians interact with SRM

A third group discussed how politicians interacted with SRM. This group was interested in seeing how politicians would act if an SRM governance system, agreed by all actors, was already implemented. Within the scenarios, they were interested in varying:

- Whether there are large effects attributable to SRM (yes, no, not sure)
- The interests of the politicians (nationalism, internationalism, ecomodernism, neoliberal greens, reelection)
- How scientific findings are communicated (alarmism or focus on uncertainties)
- Non-governmental actors (activists, environmentalist groups, sceptics, lobbyists)
- Political systems (democratic, autocratic)

They were interested in using the variation of these parameters to explore a variety of questions:

- How the public perceives the climate's reaction to SRM in response to the decisionmaking, and thus exploring which life SRM leads in public discourse.
- How businesses respond, such as the fossil fuel industry or new climate change relevant industries (eg renewables).
- How political systems will co-evolve and change with SRM, or whether it could lead to states or the world being stuck in a contradictory political system.
- How policy will be updated in response to other outcomes, including mechanisms and speed of response.
- How the governance system established at the start might evolve through time, including due to climatic, political and geopolitical changes

Group 4- Exogenous Events

This group focused on exogenous events hitting an SRM system, such as space weather and (super-)volcanic eruptions. Unfortunately, the notes for this group have either been lost, were never taken, or intermingled with the discussions for group 1.

Overall, whilst a large possibility space of scenarios was explored, and there seemed interest at exploring the response of governance systems, politicians and scientists to extreme events and situations, there was little agreement as to exactly what the scenarios should look like. There was also discussion of 'game-like' and storytelling scenarios, and both backcasting and more open ended futures.

This has then informed the carrying out of a ParEvo exercise as part of the RESILIENCER project, which allows for open ended exploration of many scenarios. This was informed by the interest in responses of governance system to climatic and non-climatic events, and how politicians and key decision makers act, but the lack of agreement as to what governance system to test made the creative, open ended, scenario exercise the most promising. This also incorporated both a quasi-backcasting phase predominantly focused on the formation of agreements (which had been proposed in group 1 and 3) and more open ended exploration of the resilience of these systems to stress testing. At the workshop to discuss the ParEvo exercise in March 2023, it is hoped that some of these scenarios will be expanded towards the end of the century, thus fulfilling some of the discussions and interests of group 2 as well.

2.5. Discussion 4: Conclusions and Next Steps

The concluding session, despite planned for an hour, lasted nearly two hours. The structure of it was far looser than the other sessions, with essentially an open forum to discuss concluding thoughts and next steps, as well as what we would like the SRM research field to look like in the future.

It was felt that the SRM field did not understand the concept of risk particularly well, and thus inclusion of more risk scholars in the field was considered to be useful. There was a suggestion that this may be a more general problem with SRM being a transdisciplinary field, terms are used with different connotations, and that this issue, and thus the need for communication with experts from different fields, was particularly necessary when exploring SRM and GCR, as both are small, transdisciplinary fields. Some participants suggested a greater exploration of risk-risk analysis with regards to GCR, between

SRM and climate change. However, this concept was challenged as assuming the risk from SRM was uncorrelated with the risk from climate change, as posing a false dichotomy, and by the suggestion that the risk from SRM and the risk from climate change is not fungible in this way.

Others continued to raise concerns about the GCR concept. Some suggested that a definition of GCR that used a 10 percentage death count was arbitrary, although another suggested that the more holistic concept of worse case compounding and cascading risk raised in SJ Beard's talk would be more appropriate. Despite worries around the GCR framing, there was general agreement as to the need to address the relation between worse-case scenarios and SRM, and it was thought this "worse case" framing was perhaps more useful than specific reference to GCR. Despite this, the worry was raised that these more pessimistic visions may gain prominence, and there was a sense that GCR should only be one consideration amongst many.

Despite this, there was significant interest in techniques that may be useful in studying GCR, even from participants who were less keen on the GCR framing. The concept of scenario generation, in particular through narrative and storytelling rather than mathematical models, was of particular interest to the participants. The modelling and science of extreme scenarios was also of interest as well. There were interest from all participants to potentially engage with scenario exercises on SRM, as well as generally a desire to expand on the GCR relevant methodologies in SRM.

There were, however, questions of how much we as the currently existing research field had the ability or right to expand the conversation around SRM. Some participants suggested that this indicated the need to include other experts, such as those around risk, in the conversation. However, others felt that this didn't go far enough, and that a general ceding of control of the field from the small group of researchers to a variety of publics was essential. These participants proposed democratic control over what values are included in scenarios by broad global publics. There was a sense from other participants, however, that such an approach promoted inaction from the SRM community due to the small size of the community and the very large amount of public engagement work being proposed, and ceded responsibility that ought not to be shifted from the researchers themselves. There was a sense that this debate was even sharper in the context of GCR and SRM interaction, as so few people were thinking about it; it may simultaneously be more essential to get broad input into normative assumptions in scenarios, but also that this was much harder in terms of the capacity of researchers to actually do this.

Finally, despite disagreements, there was a sense that there was a responsibility of the group to expand the conversation around SRM more generally. Some suggested that if SRM and GCR were important to explore, then the group gathered at the workshop had an ethical responsibility with regards to if and how this happens.

3

Appendices

3.1. Appendix 1

Below are graphs of the answers to the numerical survey sent out before the workshop, to give a sense of the initial views of the participants. 1 is strongly disagree, and 5 is strongly agree.

I understand what a Global Catastrophic Risk is
20 responses

I understand what an Existential Risk is
20 responses

SRM poses a bigger contribution to existential risk than climate change

20 responses

There is no chance that climate change contributes to civilisational collapse this century

20 responses

I think it is important to think about global catastrophic and existential risk

20 responses

If I felt I could contribute to understanding how SRM could impact global catastrophic risk, I would be interested contributing in projects that do this (eg research papers on this topic)

20 responses

If I felt I could contribute to understanding how SRM could impact global catastrophic risk, I would be interested contributing in projects that do this (eg research papers on this topic)

20 responses

The Solar Geoengineering Non-Use agreement is a positive development

20 responses

The single most important consideration with regards to whether or not a specific SRM experiment is dangerous is its direct environmental impact

20 responses

SRM research does not make SRM deployment significantly more likely

20 responses

Outdoor SRM research poses a uniquely serious type of moral hazard when compared to modelling studies

20 responses

SRM research could significantly reduce the likelihood of dangerous SRM deployment

20 responses

It is possible to have a comprehensive definition of SRM research which isn't just focused on the intention of researchers

20 responses

In general, scientific inquiry shouldn't be restricted, and SRM is no exception

20 responses

3.2. Appendix 2

3.2.1. The Descriptions

Description 1

The volcanology department at the University of Krakoa has decided to carry out an experiment observing the evolution of volcanic plumes in the stratosphere, by injecting inert tracer gases into a volcanic plume and observing the spatio-temporal evolution of this. This is seen as vital at predicting the behaviour of volcanic plumes, which due to the recent interest in catastrophic risks of volcanos, is now seen as a major research priority. The experiment has passed university ethical approval, with negligible environmental dangers of the experiment. A number of newspaper articles focus on this initiative, claiming "Scientists do first of a kind study to see if volcanoes could kill us all!", each focusing on the concept of volcano Global Catastrophic Risk and the questions it argues. No newspaper article mentions SRM. [Is it the experiment itself? Is it communication?] **1st Added information:** The key designer of the experiment, Peter Parker, is clearly aware SRM exists, as he has written about it in the context of wanting to do the opposite with volcano geoengineering. Charles Xavier, a relatively prominent member of the SRM Research community, joins onto the project to assist on observing the effects of the aerosols on the stratosphere. [Is it the people involved?] The paper directly released as a recording of the experiments results makes no mention of SRM. Moreover, the press releases focus entirely on the reduction in uncertainties around volcanic catastrophic risk. However, a paper by one of the authors later that year about the implication of the experiment comments on its utility in reducing uncertainties around SRM. This paper has zero citations. [Is it where the results of the experiment place it?]

2nd added information After the additional experiment, amongst other funding sources, the experimenters secure funding from Open Philanthropy, a private funder who has in the past funded SRM research (such as DECIMALS) as part of their project funding global catastrophic risks in general. [Is it funders?] This allows the experiment to be expanded, and with a now renewed focus on microphysics. Thus, to get a better idea of plume microphysics, planes act to simulate small scale volcanic plumes in the upper troposphere, at the tropopause and in the lower stratosphere, and the microphysical and chemical evolution of these plumes are observed. [Is it a different experiment?] ETC Group adds this to their list of SRM experiments and suggests this experiment is an unacceptable backdoor way of doing SRM experiments, but the study authors deny strongly that this experiment has anything to do with SRM. [Is it interpretation?]

3rd added information: A year after the study is published, the Harvard Geoengineering Programme publishes a number of papers highlighting how the results of the study are exceptionally useful in the study of SRM, and modellers start incorporating the results into models. These models are then utilised to study SRM further. [Is it who the study would be used by? Does it become SRM research at this point?]

Description 2

A PhD student in the plant science department at the University of Oxford has carried out an experiment observing the impact of changing light quality on ecosystem. She carries out an ecosystem manipulation experiment where areas of forest are covered in a canopy which modulates the quality and quantity of light coming to the ecosystem. She then compares the way that growth rates are changed due to that light. There is no media coverage of the project. No one who works on the project has previously worked on anything that could be considered SRM related. [Is it the experiment itself?] **Additional Information:** The study reveals that an increase in diffuse light outweighs the negative impacts of a slight decrease in total light, and that the ecosystems under the SRM-like cover performed the best. In the initial study, the applications to SRM are essentially not mentioned. This study is mentioned in a short perspectives piece in nature by [insert SRM scholar] of why SRM benefits ecosystems. [Is it what the results are used for?] **Additional Information- Alternative** The study reveals that the ecosystems under the SRM-like cover performed the worst. In the discussion section of the initial study where applications are mentioned, this is mentioned, suggesting it shows that SRM will have a negative impacts on ecosystems. Other applications, such as the information it gives about tropospheric aerosol pollution, volcanic eruptions etc are also mentioned. Media coverage and explicit public communication of the paper focuses on the implications on SRM [Is it what the study says? Is it the communication?]

Additional Information- Alternative 2 This experiment was explicitly set up to assess the effects of SRM changes to light quality on ecosystems. The experiment reveals that SRM benefits ecosystem

growth. This is published and presented at conferences, but explicitly no media coverage. [Is it study design/intention?]

Description 3

Harvard Solar Geoengineering Program carries out a large scale modelling study into the impacts of a variety of politically feasible SRM deployment schemes on temperature and precipitation, and then link this to ecosystem impacts and food production. Then then combine this with climate damages models, and compare this to various IPCC scenarios. From this, they conclude that SRM would significantly reduce climate damages. The paper that lays this out is published in Nature. This result is reported in various mainstream media outlets. [Is it the experiment? Is it the institution?] Additional Information 1 When interviewed for these, Scott Summers, who founded the Harvard Geoengineering Programme, suggests that given mounting climate damages SRM may look increasingly attractive, and should be taken seriously as a possibility. [Is it the communication?] Alternative information 1 The same paper is published, however it comes to opposite conclusions, negative to SRM and its impacts. It finds all deployment schemes tested are considerably worse than previously thought. This is similarly published in nature and reported widely[Is it the outcome?] Alternative additional information 1 The paper, whilst concluding SRM is considerably worse than thought, also suggests more research should be done on the ways to reduce harm from SRM, alternative deployment schemes etc. This paper on this topic, using similar modelling techniques, is published, outlining ways these deployment schemes could be made less damaging. [Is it assessment vs development research?]

3.3. Appendix 3

3.3.1. The Tripartite Framework

I characterise the nascent SRM science research ecosystem by three intersecting components; the Communities, which is the primary site of research, the Research, which is the output of the Communities, and Communication, which is how the Research is communicated within various aspects of the Communities to the outside world. The first of the three intersecting components to explore is the social organisation of the SRM research ecosystem, which I deem the Communities. These Communities carry out many activities; they are the site of research and innovation, the actors who communicate do so within them, they carry out engagement to formulate publics, are where socio-technical imaginaries are formed and can be seen as both the wielders of power and where actors wield power. Importantly, the concept of Communities is both a plural and a singular. Depending on the scale one wants to look at it, the Communities contains many different thought collectives, with different and competing discourses, requiring translation between them. So the ecosystem could be conceptualised as containing many thought collectives with translational zones between them. Alternatively, the Communities can also be seen as a more singular grouping, with power structures within it and respect dictated by discourses common in the academy, stretching from an esoteric group within common academic discussions, to an exoteric group which at its extreme contains those with no knowledge of the socio-technical imaginaries which the Communities use to define SRM.

Formal communities describes those institutions or processes with well defined, spatio-temporally constrained, often legally codified, structures or existences, including research groups [11], conferences [3], civil society organisations [6][2], and integration of outside research organisations [18] or funding organisations [21] into the ecosystem. Formal communities is not synonymous with the "big science" aspects of the SRM research ecosystem, but is strongly related to it. Informal social groups include both small and large scale groupings, including quasi-defined informal groupings (which seem to exist in the intersection of formal and informal communities) [9][4], but also harder to define groupings, such as "invisible colleges" [30], "thought collectives" [8] and the broader research communities working on SRM.

Knowledge is generating the basic science and engineering knowledge which can then be useful in assessment or development of SRM, but is nonetheless broadly applicable. Knowledge research, whilst similar to the concept of basic research, is distinct by the fact it is only "basic" with regards to SRM, and in fact much "knowledge research" would be considered applied research in the more general sense, such as [22]. Moreover, it is arguable that some studies of SRM that would be considered "basic research" would not be considered knowledge research under my model, such as those carried out by Oomen's basic scientist classification [19]. Knowledge research can only be linked to SRM by its intention, and often can't be physically distinguished from other types of research, as shown in the LEISE report [cite when its published] Thus, the subdivisions of this are defined by their intention, and

the methodologies used and the results produced may not differ between the subdivisions. Application is the linking of knowledge research into the context of SRM. We take this to have two key subdivisions; development and assessment. Development intends to increase the effectiveness of the technology and make effective and safe deployment more likely, whereas assessment attempts to assess the impacts of different deployment schemes, [20] Development application research may include engineering designs [13], attempts to improve possible deployment [25] and development of detection methods [15] whereas assessment application research involves assessing the risks and benefits of specific scenarios. Both may include both natural and social scientific research. A large amount of this distinction is related to intention; development ostensibly intends to leave decision makers in a position where they could choose to carry out as safe and effective deployment scheme as possible if they so wished -whether it can or does achieve this is questionable- , whereas assessment merely assesses the impacts of specific schemes [28].

Communication refers to the way in which SRM is communicated to the out-group. This can include explicit communication, such as media articles [7], talks [12] and podcasts [16], or implicit communication, such as the very existence of research programmes causing a moral hazard[29]. Such communication can be created by both those based within the SRM community and outside of it[23]. Communication is forms information sharing and messaging that are beyond the traditionally "in group" methods of dispersal, namely academic papers and conferences, with the aim on consequence of directly influencing out-group thought on this. So dispersal by diffusion would not, for example, be considered communication, nor is the portrayal of results in papers and the rhetoric used in papers themselves necessarily communication, but press releases or tweets are. Whilst it might be contended that this framework neglects that the way rhetoric used in research has normative implications, including these impacts under the sub-division of "research" seems both more natural and clearer. Nonetheless, it is clear that this rhetoric can play a role in the relationship between research and communication.

Explicit and implicit communication are both subdivided into "neutral" and "messaging" framings. Of course, both of these have normative implications; however the "neutral" framing doesn't do this explicitly but rather presents itself as neutral presentation of "facts", which is in contrast to the more explicit normativity of messaging framings, with the normative aspects implicit rather than explicit.

In this way, knowledge research into SRM can be sub-divided by how intentional it is positioned in relation to the research questions necessary to support application research. Less explicitly connected is unintentional research where the authors of the research are (seemingly) unaware of any applicability of their research to SRM, for example [14] and [22]. Secondly, there is incidental knowledge research, where the researchers are aware of the application of the research to SRM, but this is not a motivating concern, for example [17] . Thirdly, there is hidden research, where the research is not explicitly an SRM experiment, but the authors likely had an application to SRM as a motivating factor, for example seemingly the E-PEACE study [24] Finally, intentional knowledge research, where the research is linked to questions from application throughout the process, for example [5]. Intentional knowledge research can be seen as Stoke's concept of use-orientated basic research applied to this typology [26].

3.4. Appendix 4

What is a global catastrophe?	What is a global catastrophe?	What is the risk of a global catastrophe?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global Catastrophes are the very worst things that can happen to us and would negatively impact our entire planet COVID-19 may end up causing 20-30 million deaths worldwide (0.3-0.4% of the global population). This would be less than the HIV/AIDS pandemic (40 million deaths or 0.5% of the global population) or World War 1 (18 million deaths or 1% of the global population in 1918) It is far less than the 1918 influenza (50 million deaths) or World War 2 (75 million deaths) both of which killed about 3% of the global population A global catastrophe would be worse than any of these 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A global catastrophe is something with "the potential to inflict serious damage to human well-being on a global scale" (Bostrom and Cirkovic 2008) One common definition of a Global Catastrophe is an event that would kill at least 10% of the global population in a short period of time, equivalent to the Black Death or Plague of Justinian (Cotton-Barratt et al 2016) Another is that Global Catastrophes are disasters "beyond the collective capability of national and international governments and the private sector to control" (Schoch-Spana et al. 2017) At the extreme end are existential catastrophes that might cause human extinction or civilization collapse 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We might experience a global or existential catastrophe at some point in the next century, or we might not – that is why this is a risk. In general we would expect more extreme catastrophes to be less likely than less extreme ones. However, given the presence of tipping points in many of the critical systems we rely on this may not be the case. More extreme global catastrophes should worry us more. It is harder to prepare for them and harder to recover from them. An existential catastrophe is one from which our society, or even our species, cannot recover. We might care more about this because we care about future generations, or because it is a tragic outcome, but we should also simply care about it more because it would be worse for people.

The nature of global catastrophic risk	Classifying global catastrophes	Classifying global catastrophes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global catastrophic risk is a risk, not an event (notwithstanding the fact that many common definitions equivocate between these) We need to talk about Global Catastrophic Risk rather than Global Catastrophic Risks. We can differentiate between different kinds of global catastrophe (e.g. global winter, technological failures) and different drivers of Global Catastrophic Risk (e.g. nuclear weapons, volcanoes) but there is no simple one to one mapping between these. Global Catastrophic Risk is not an exogenous variable, it depends heavily on decision making and governance failures, even if these are only failures of risk preparedness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Global catastrophes can be characterized by 1) failures of critical systems on which humanity depends and 2) mechanisms by which these failures spread around the world and also from system to system There are many critical systems that we rely on from basic physics and human physiology, though biogeochemical and ecological systems, up to sociotechnological systems Critical systems will typically have a safe operating space in which they continue to provide the support we need but they can also cross safety boundaries that push them outside of this space System failures can spread via natural global scale mechanisms, anthropogenic network mechanisms, or biological or informational replication. 	

Classifying the drivers of risk	The connections between risk drivers and global catastrophes	Classifying the anthropogenic factors in GCR
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Like all risks, we can understand GCR as being driven by 3 components Hazards/threats – the external source of peril i.e. the factor that leads to system diabatization such as a volcano, greenhouse gasses, or AI Vulnerabilities – "propensities or weaknesses inherent within human social, political, economic or legal systems, that increase the likelihood of humanity succumbing to pressures or challenges that threaten existential outcomes" i.e. the source of our dependence upon a system such as our ecological interdependence or social complexity exposures – "the number, scope and nature of the interface between the hazard and the vulnerability" i.e. the system states that are dangerous for us, such as overextension of our food supply or limited healthcare resources, and why we are unable to prevent these 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sometimes a set of risk drivers can produce an existential catastrophe directly, such as an unaligned AI or engineered pathogen that simply kills everyone Sometimes risk drivers interact to bring about a global catastrophe, such as a climate induced conflict leading to a nuclear war Sometimes risk drivers cause sub global catastrophes but these create system perturbations that end up being catastrophic, such as a pandemic that undermines the global economy and stifles co-operation on reducing other drivers of risk Sometimes risk drivers serve as a latent risk, creating a potential for global catastrophes that may be triggered later, such as a creation of a dangerous technology that isn't used but can't be put back in the box 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GCRs exist because of a range of governance failures, some of which relate to our 'semi-anarchic default position' (Bostrom 2019) Some drivers of risk are outside of our control but could be reduced if humanity is prepared for them (e.g. the hazard of volcanoes or our biological vulnerability) Some drivers of risk are created by our ability to externalize costs and/or internalize benefits (e.g. our destabilization of the biosphere) Some drivers of risk are created by the imperative to develop technology faster and cheaper than is safe (e.g. because of race mentalities) Some drivers of risk are created by a desire to cause harm and a lack of incentives not to do so (e.g. nuclear weapons or extractive capitalism)

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